

Deep Learning Multi-State Models for Individualized Risk Prediction in Multiple Myeloma

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Abstract. Multiple myeloma (MM) is a complex and highly heterogeneous hematologic malignancy. Despite frequent advancements in therapy approaches, MM remains incurable, with patients experiencing multiple relapses during different disease stages and a wide range of overall survival. This variability in disease progression highlights the need for a personalized risk assessment. While traditional risk stratification methods provide prognostic insights, they primarily focus on newly diagnosed patients and fail to address the complexities of relapsed MM, where prior treatments can significantly impact outcomes. We utilize a discrete-time deep learning multi-state modeling approach to predict and simulate patient trajectories across multiple lines of therapy and disease stages, while incorporating clinical, genetic, and treatment covariates. Developed within the CERTAINTY project, the models aim to enhance individualized risk prediction and are designed to serve as a decision support system in clinical practice.

Keywords: Multi-state models · risk prediction · multiple myeloma

1 Background

Multiple myeloma (MM) is a plasma cell malignancy characterized by the clonal proliferation of malignant cells within the bone marrow. These malignant cells produce an abnormal monoclonal antibody (M protein), whose type significantly influences both disease prognosis and the associated biomarkers. Due to the inherent heterogeneity of MM, accurate risk assessment plays a crucial role in guiding therapeutic decisions. Traditionally, the International Staging System (ISS) has served as the foundation for risk stratification in MM. However, advancements in biomarker discovery [10] and novel therapeutic approaches have led to the development of more detailed methods. For instance, the revised ISS (R-ISS) [9] and the R2-ISS [2], which incorporate additional prognostic markers,

such as further high-risk chromosomal abnormalities, provide more nuanced risk evaluations.

Recent studies have shown the advantages of deep learning and AI-based models for personalized risk prediction, which can incorporate high-dimensional, multimodal data including clinical variables, individual disease characteristics, genomics, and longitudinal biomarkers. These approaches support personally tailored therapeutic decision making and have outperformed classical staging systems in risk stratification and prediction [8].

However, current risk assessment approaches remain largely focused on newly diagnosed MM (NDMM) patients. This leaves a significant gap in the ability to assess risk for patients with refractory/relapsed MM (RRMM), an area of critical importance given that MM remains incurable, and patients eventually experience disease progression. Past treatments can significantly influence the outcomes of subsequent therapies, highlighting the need for risk assessment strategies that account for the unique challenges of RRMM [1].

2 Methods

In recent years, deep learning models for risk prediction and survival analysis have been shown to outperform traditional approaches like the Cox proportional hazards model [11]. While some of these approaches extend the Cox regression framework by parametrizing the log-risk function using neural networks (e.g., DeepSurv [4] and CoxTime [5]), other models directly estimate the underlying distribution without relying on specific stochastic assumptions (e.g., DeepHit [7]). Multi-state models, which can be seen as an extension of time-to-event models [3], aim to estimate the transition probabilities and hazards for a patient across an arbitrary number of states. These models have proven particularly useful for risk prediction in complex diseases such as multiple myeloma [8]. However, existing multi-state modeling approaches often rely on a combination of single time-to-event models for each possible transition, which can limit their flexibility and accuracy.

To address these challenges, we propose a discrete-time multi-state model based on a Markov chain approach to model a patient’s trajectory across multiple lines of therapy and disease stages. This model evaluates the state of a patient at fixed time intervals (e.g., monthly or quarterly) and directly estimates the transition matrix using neural networks. To incorporate longitudinal patient information, we utilize state-specific subnetworks that encode the current and prior treatments for each line of therapy separately. Additionally, transition-specific subnetworks are designed to capture non-proportional and non-linear risks, enabling a more flexible and accurate representation of the dynamics of disease progression and treatment response.

3 Experiments

We compare our approach with existing risk prediction models using real-world data on NDMM and RRMM, focusing on their performance in predicting key clinical outcomes, such as overall survival, progression-free survival, and event-free survival. We evaluate the advantages of a multi-state approach for assessing treatment outcomes across multiple lines of therapy. Furthermore, we adapt gradient-based, model-specific explanation methods from the survival analysis setting [6] to our multi-state framework, to explore the importance of treatment covariates on different events and outcomes over time.

Data. For our experiments, we utilize real-world electronic health records, laboratory results, and molecular genetic data provided by TriNetX Oncology GmbH as part of the CERTAINTY project (collected from multiple healthcare facilities). The data contains patients receiving up to 7 lines of therapy, making it especially suitable for risk prediction in RRMM.

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